

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Mala Ijalla**FIRST NAME:** Stephen Fritz**PROGRAM CODE:** DDIA**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 01**INSTRUCTOR:** DR. KABIRU**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Basics of essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-5)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Literature review (EUCLID 2019, 17-22)
4. Study guide (EUCLID 2019, 24)
5. American vs British (EUCLID 2019, 27-34)
6. Latin Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56)
7. Chicago Style (EUCLID 2019, 44-48)

IMPROVING ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have been writing most of my career using English as the official language in my country (Uganda) including meetings presentations, e-mails, business reports, and so on. Before I enrolled in EUCLID, I had many questions for example, is there any difference in writing a EUCLID paper with the reports that I have been writing? Or will I find so much difficulty in learning how EUCLID presents its papers? When finally I enrolled and started learning the ACA-401 period one course, I was given several study materials including a video and coursepack entailing the guidelines for writing a Response Paper (RP). I noticed that there was a difference in EUCLID to other courses that I have enrolled in before. The course provides study materials to help me improve my academic writing for instance with the video of 14 minutes and ACA-401 period one (1) coursepack helped me know what to do while writing my academic papers, not only the response paper but be able to apply the knowledge obtained to writing other papers be it business reports, thesis, research reports, and others.

2) **BASICS OF ESSAY WRITING**

In the coursepack I was given, chapter one of the ACA-401 for period one entails the basics of essay writing. It starts with a question, “*what does a good essay need?*” I learned that a good academic essay should answer a question or task, a thesis statement, an argument, present something and include relevant examples (EUCLID 2019, 1). Given the different definitions of an essay, I will present one definition according to toppr.com, the word ‘essay’ is derived from a Latin word ‘exagium,’ which roughly translates to presenting one’s case. Toppr.com defines an essay as generally a short piece of writing outlining the writer’s perspective or story. It is often considered to be synonymous with a story or a paper or an article (<https://www.toppr.com/guides/essays/>). I agree with the definition and consider an academic essay as a paper, article, or story that I will submit to EUCLID.

The basics of essay writing are vital in academics and I advise that every learning institution should endeavor to teach students how best they can write their papers. In Uganda for example, few learning institutions have coursepacks that teach students the basics of academic writing. According to EUCLID (2019, 1), the basic steps needed in writing an essay include analyzing the question and defining key terms; establishing a possible thesis or point of view; researching the topic by use of credible academic sources for support and evidence; taking notes from your readings; writing an essay plan and organizing ideas; writing the first draft to include an introduction, body, and conclusion; setting the draft aside for a day or two, then read it through and make changes; editing and redrafting the essay; having a friend, parent or colleague read it; completing or checking the references and bibliography, and completing final draft then hand it in. I believe these steps are vital in writing an academic paper because writing down everything about a topic may not be sufficient to make a good academic essay however, analyzing, then answering the essay’s question or task is central (ibid.).

According to ACA-401, it is beneficial to write an academic essay basing on evidence because writing the opinions may not be sufficient to convince the reader that you are telling the truth. Using already researched materials gives the reader confidence while reading your paper. Further, the coursepack one advises that start reading early, so you have plenty of time to familiarize yourself with the topic and develop your ideas. When you look at your readings more closely, remember to read with a purpose (ibid.). Another technique needed in writing an essay is researching because researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question. In terms of organization, an essay needs organized ideas to help one structure how the essay will look like.

Another basic of academic essay writing is its structure and according to EUCLID (2019, 3), all essays should be communicated through three sections, that is to say, introduction, body, and conclusion. Each paragraph of the body of the essay should deal with one main point or aspect of your answer. I noticed that I should make sure I am familiar with the referencing style my Faculty or School requires. This will help eliminate

plagiarism in the work. I was pleased with coursepack one because it showed me that as I write my academic essays, I need to edit it thoroughly to improve my work.

3) PLAGIARISM

Original writing materials are very important because it adds information to already the existing one. However, if one writes an academic paper while copying and pasting the works of others without acknowledging them it is very unacceptable in the academic fraternity. This is called plagiarism. According to Wikipedia, “plagiarism is the representation of another author's language, thoughts, ideas, or expressions as one's original work”. Plagiarism might not be the same in all countries. Some countries, such as India and Poland, consider plagiarism to be a crime, and there have been cases of people being imprisoned for plagiarizing (<https://www.plagiarism.org/blog/2017/10/27/is-plagiarism-illegal>). Therefore, while writing an academic essay, the writer should endeavor to give credit to the author. This should be done when there is the use of any statistic or data, quote, paraphrase, or visuals (such as a graph) that is borrowed from another source (EUCLID 2019, 5). I was pleased to learn that one way to avoid plagiarism is to give credit to the source or author of information being cited.

In chapter two of the coursepack period one, there is a section “Quotations” which elaborates that “when you use a quotation, you must use quotation marks “.....” to capture what the author has said” (EUCLID 2019, 6). I was previously pretty confused about how to use someone else’s work in my essay however, after reading chapter two; I can now comfortably use quotations while citing the exact words of the author. However, there are instances when citations are not needed especially while writing about things that require common knowledge, for example, smoking causes lung cancer. It causes a little effect to cite that. The coursepack gave the full description of how best I can write my academic essay without any issues of plagiarism and it easy for me to comply with what EUCLID holds against plagiarism.

4) LITERATURE REVIEW

I have witnessed time and time again that an academic paper such as a research paper does not stand ground for discussion without a literature review. According to Wikipedia, “a literature review is a scholarly paper that presents the current knowledge including substantive findings as well as theoretical and methodological contributions to a particular topic. Literature reviews are secondary sources and do not report new or original experimental work. Most often associated with academic-oriented literature, such reviews are found in academic journals and are not to be confused with book reviews, which may also appear in the same publication”. In the coursepack for period one, there are several elements elaborated in it to enable one to learn how to write the literature review well. For instance, ACA-401 in chapter four poses a question, how many spaces go after a period? I am thankful that one space should be typed after any punctuation

(EUCLID 2019, 18) and this removes my confusion of whether two spaces should be typed after a period. I learned that a comma should go between the second to last item and the conjunction (i.e., "and" or "or"). Can you begin a sentence with "and"? A question is posed in the coursepack. I learned that when "and" is used properly; it can create a really good sentence in an academic essay. In this chapter I learned that there are many things to consider when writing the literature review and I am pleased with the outcome of studying that chapter.

5) STYLE GUIDE

Chapter five of the course pack explains what a style guide is and why a student may need one. According to EUCLID (2019, 24), a style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent. Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. It elaborates that in each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent and so guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with a large number of contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent.

a) Chicago style and usage

I am pleased to learn that EUCLID recommends the use of Turabian (Chicago Rules) though they are many recommended styles internationally that can be used. Turabian style is sometimes referred to as the Chicago style (EUCLID 2019, 44). According to (Services n.d.), citations in Chicago style use footnotes that appear at the bottom of the page and all items cited in the text will also appear in the Bibliography. We are not allowed to use lowercases while beginning a sentence in Chicago style. However, many traditional styles are allowed to be used such as Dr., Mr., Ms., and others. Therefore abbreviations should only be used when they are clear to the readers. In terms of civilization, we are generally only allowed to capitalize on major words and the first word after a colon or dash in titles and headings within the body of the paper (ibid.). While italics to a word or phrase can only be used the first time, thereafter a plain text is used. In the general rules of quotations, The Turabian manual advises that "in general a prose quotation of two or more sentences that runs to eight or more lines of text in a paper should be set off from the text in single-spacing and indented in its entirety from the left margin" (EUCLID 2019, 48).

6) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

I come from a country that was colonized by the British that means most schools use British English in class. However, over the years of my studies, I have come to notice

that there are quite many differences in American and British English. The British introduced English to the American people in the 16th and 17th century though at that time spellings had not been standardized. It is the introduction of the dictionary that created a difference between the two languages. The American dictionary which was compiled by Noah Webster who allegedly changed how words were spelled and he was motivated by the need to create a cultural difference between the Americans and the British. Certain words have the same pronunciation with different meanings for example Cheque and Check, ageing and aging, and so on. Certain words are spelt differently for example, the British term for a condition in which the blood does not have enough healthy red blood cells as anaemia while the Americans spell it as anemia, also the word cancelled in British and canceled in Americans both mean the same, a decision that a planned event will not take place. There are many other examples. These words have the same meanings but different spellings. EUCLID allows students to use American English. Therefore, with the ACA-401, I am pleased to have learnt the major differences between British and American English and ways to apply American English in my academic writing given the scenario that I am from a country with a British background.

7) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

I have come to learn during this coursepack in chapter nine that some of the words that I have been using are Latin terms. According to (“Latin Terms and Abbreviations” n.d.), while it is perfectly acceptable to use English phrases instead of Latin abbreviations, there’s a reason why these abbreviations have survived and continue to be used today: they contain a lot of meaning in a very small package. It takes less time and fewer characters to write e.g. than “for example.” As a bonus, using Latin abbreviations correctly can make your writing sound more sophisticated and scholarly. There are so many abbreviations used today such as e.g., a.m., p.m., cv., N.B., and so on; all with their origins of Latin and meaning. Some people find it easier to use e.g. than “for example”, etc., than “et cetera” and so on. These abbreviations are used worldwide by scholars writing their academic papers, they use “et al.” (*et alia*), in instances where the authors of the book they are citing are many instead of noting all of them (EUCLID 2019, 57).

8) CONCLUSION

This coursepack is my initial stage in pursuing my doctorate in Diplomacy and International Affairs. I have learned plenty of things from the 14 minute video and ACA-401 period one (1) coursepack. From reading the study material (ACA-401), I am satisfied with the guidelines and I am pleased to apply them in forthcoming courses. I have been able to learn the basics of writing an academic paper and I noted that writing down everything about a topic may not be sufficient to make a good academic essay however, analyzing, then answering the essay’s question or task is central. More so, I have the skills now to write evidenced-based essays while avoiding plagiarism.

On the side of the style, I have noticed that EUCLID allows students to use Turabian Style that reflects its need. The style allows me to cite easily while doing my academic work. This course has given me techniques to write literature properly and I believe that I will put a comma between the second to last item and the conjunction (i.e., "and" or "or"), when I use a quotation, I ensure use quotation marks "...” to capture what the author has said”. The coursepack has given light to get prepared and research a lot before writing any academic paper. I am certain that this course pack, ACA-401 will be beneficial as I pursue my doctorate at EUCLID.

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